

Observations of can Bus Control System

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ABSTRACT

One of the important criteria of the modern cars is digital control of the vehicle. Because of the quick development of embedded technology, the high performance embedded processor is inserted into auto industry; it has low cost, high reliability and other features that meet the needs of modern automobile industry. In this project we have introduced an embedded system which is a combination of different CAN bus systems.

KEY WORDS: CAN, LM35

I. MCP 2515

Microchip technologies MCP 2515 is a controller area network (CAN).It has the ability to transmit and receive both remote and data frames. The MCP2515 has two acceptance masks and six acceptance filters that are used to clean the unwanted messages.

The MCP 2515 has three pins that can be designed as general purpose inputs and two pins that are designed as digital output.The inputs are connected to switch contacts and the outputs to the LED indicators.The MCP 2515 also have internal pull-up resistors.

Before communicating with the CAN bus, the MCP2515 should be properly configured. The configuration is achieved by loading the control registers with the specific value. During MCP2515 initialization these values are read via SPI interface. The MCP 2515 interfaces with microcontrollers (MCUs) via SPI i.e. serial peripheral interface.

Figure 1: MCP 2515

II. SPI BUS-

SPI makes use of different clock,select and data lines to choose the device you wish to talk to.SPI devices communicate in full duplex mode.The SPI bus operates with a single master device and one or more slave devices.

The standard SPI interface has been modified here which uses common signal line for both serial in(SI) and serial out(SO) lines.These lines have been isolated from each other via resistor.This method requires three I/O pins to implement SPI interface.

III. CAN BUS MODULE PIN OUT AND CONNECTION-

Figure 2: CAN Bus Module

There are variety of CAN applications which include vehicles (via OBDII or J1939) and industrial monitoring and controls. The CAN node is interrupt driven which has the ability of monitoring five external inputs (i.e. two analog and three digital) and automatically creating messages based on their value. This node also controls two digital outputs. The system supports maximum CAN bus speed of 125kbps.

IV. TEMPERATURE SENSOR

Temperature sensor is basically used to sense the temperature. We have used a Temperature sensor named LM35. This temperature sensor has the ability to sense the temperature of the atmosphere around it

7. LI, Q. and X. ZHANG, Development of Embedded RTOS uClinux on ARM. Journal of Changchun University of Science and Technology (Natural Science Edition), 2009. **32**(2): p. 264-267.
8. Li, M., Design of Embedded Remote Temperature Monitoring System Based on Advanced RISC Machine. Electrotechnics Electric, 2009. **6**.
9. Zhang, Q.S., et al., Application of Embedded Technology for Induced Polarization Instrument. Advanced Materials Research, 2012. **383**: p. 224-229.
10. Prodanov, W., M. Valle, and R. Buzas, A controller area network bus transceiver behavioral model for network design and simulation. IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics, 2009. **56**(9): p. 3762- 3771. 442

